

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-136-IG-5% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	39	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 136
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	280.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 280.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/19/2022 4:01:54 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 11:25:48 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.624	753529	35.06	54791
2	10.988	798109	37.13	45111
3	11.829	298585	13.89	15673
4	30.352	299109	13.92	5001

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-127-IG-5% ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20221119
Vial:	8	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 127
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	280.0nm
Run Time:	33.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 280.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/19/2022 9:50:41 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 3:44:28 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.627	6248506	98.99	456134
2	11.014	826	0.01	116
3	11.876	59285	0.94	3129
4	30.426	3407	0.05	184